

PREPARING PRIMARY STUDENTS FOR THE TIMSS INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT PROGRAM

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Abstract: This article can be used by primary school teachers in preparing primary school students for the TIMSS international assessment program and in the pedagogical activities of graduate students.

Keywords: Primary education, pedagogy, educational effectiveness, educational technologies, assessment systems, teaching methods , specific tasks , level of education .

Uzbekistan is currently in the process of developing primary education based on international experience and standards. Certain tasks have been set in this regard [1]. One of these tasks is to study the effectiveness of primary education based on international assessment programs. In this article, we draw your attention to the analysis of issues related to using the TIMSS international assessment program in assessing the effectiveness of primary education.

The TIMSS international assessment program was developed and implemented by the International Association for the Evaluation of the Process of Learning in 1995 [2]. This international assessment program studies the level of mastery of mathematics and natural sciences of 4th grade students every four years and develops recommendations in this area. The basis of the program is formed by:

- the level of students' desire to learn;
- the level of mathematical thinking of students;
- the level of students' mastery of natural sciences;
- the degree to which students use their acquired knowledge.

As is known, the basics of mathematics and natural sciences (the world around us, natural science) are taught in the primary education system of our country. For this reason, the level of students' mastery in these subjects is measured using the TIMSS international assessment program. Learning by doing will yield practical results. To achieve this, following these steps will yield the expected results:

- create a special test based on this program;
- selecting a group of students using a test;
- conducting a test among a selected group of students;
- analyze the results of the tests conducted and develop recommendations for enhanced teaching of mathematics and natural sciences in primary grades.

The TIMSS international assessment program envisages several variants of learning tests. The tests are structured according to the following principles:

- full coverage of academic subjects;
- the test should be understandable to the participating students;
- the structure of test questions from simple to complex;
- reflection of the most basic issues of mathematics and natural sciences;
- the use of the test is universal. The test, built on the basis of these principles, allows you to accurately determine the knowledge, thinking and independent behavior skills of primary school

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students based on this international program. Today, more than a hundred countries around the world are studying the primary education process based on the TIMSS international assessment program. It is worth noting that primary school students in the Russian Federation and the United States of America continue to occupy the leading positions. This indicates that the primary education process in these countries is organized on the basis of modern requirements.

It is worth noting that the TIMSS international assessment program is based on the primary. In order to study the level of knowledge, skills and education of students, it is necessary to implement a number of measures. In our opinion, the main ones of such measures are the following:

- to introduce future primary school teachers to the basics of such international assessment programs in the process of higher pedagogical education;
- include training on international assessment programs in teacher training and retraining courses;
- Conducting scientific research on international assessment programs;
- developing a methodology for studying the effectiveness of primary education based on international assessment programs.

The goal of this is to develop primary education in our country in line with international experience. For this reason, in the following pages, we will recall that we have analyzed several international assessment programs.

Based on the TIMSS international assessment program, the following method is expected to yield the expected results: 1) Conducted among 4th grade students; 2) Conducted when these students are in 8th grade. The goal is to study how students' mastery of mathematics and natural sciences and their level of independent thinking has increased over the past four years. Because students master the basic content of mathematics and natural sciences in grades 5, 6, 7, and 8. Thus, studying the effectiveness of primary education based on international assessment programs such as TIMSS provides an important basis for determining the level of students' self-determination and independent thinking. As a result of such studies, information is obtained about promising directions for the development of primary education and the possibility of implementing specific measures based on them. As a result, the foundations for developing primary education in our country in accordance with modern requirements have been laid.

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